

(ii) *Polyalkylation*: A mixture of phenol (10 mmoles), sodium hydroxide (15 mmoles for each hydroxyl group), alkylating agent (15 mmoles for each hydroxyl group) and quaternary ammonium bromide (0.1-0.5 mmole) in water (50 ml) and chloroform (50 ml) as an organic solvent was stirred at room temp. for 0.5-4 hr. The product was isolated following the same work-up procedure as in the case of monoalkylations.

(iii) *Benzylation*: The reaction is carried out at boiling water bath temp. in CH_2Cl_2 as organic solvent.

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was used as catalyst in all the cases.

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Studies in Fluorinated 1,3-Diketones and Related Compounds. Part-XVI: Studies in Lanthanide 1,3-Diketonates as NMR Shift Reagents

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FLUORINATED 1,3-diketones and related compounds are indispensable reagents in analytical chemistry and some of the most recent uses are in analysing lunar samples¹, cobalt in vitamin B₁₂ and in detection of other trace elements in blood, serum and other essential biological materials. In 1969, Hinckley² discovered that the addition of bis-pyridine adduct of *tris*-dipivalomethanatoeuropium produced downfield shift in cholesterol. Since then, the paramagnetic lanthanide(III) 1,3-diketonates are used as nmr shift reagents and the fluorinated 1,3-diketonates act as superior nmr shift reagents due to their stronger interaction with nucleophiles, (viz., ethers, ketones, alcohols, esters and amines). This is most likely due to the increased acidity of the fluorinated chelates and decrease in the basicity of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and increased solubility. Recently, we have undertaken a comprehensive programme to develop the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones³ and related compounds⁴ and as a part of this, we reported the synthesis of some new fluorinated lanthanide 1,3-diketonates⁵. We now report

their ability to act as nmr shift reagents with particular reference to shifts produced in *n*-hexanol and *p*-fluoroaniline. The following compounds synthesized earlier by us⁶ have been examined as nmr shift reagents.

1. [4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III).
2. [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-Heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato]praseodymium(III).
3. [4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]samarium(III).

Experimental

The appropriate lanthanide chloride (0.004 mole), dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol, was added very slowly to the methanolic solution of 1, 3-diketonato enolate anion (0.012 mole) (generated by dissolving the corresponding 1,3-diketone in methanol and then adding 2% methanolic sodium hydroxide solution). The lanthanide 1,3-diketonate was precipitated by slow addition of a ten fold excess of water to the resulting methanolic solution. The precipitated lanthanide 1,3-diketonates were crystallized from dichloromethane or benzene. Finally, they were dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 hr.

General procedure for observing shifts: In a clean and dry nmr sample tube, was taken a definite amount of lanthanide 1,3-diketonate, which had been dried in a drying pistol. CDCl_3 was then added to it followed by definite number of drops of alcohol or amine. NMR spectra were taken after a regular interval of time, viz., 1, 2, 3, 4, 24 hr. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the data observed, it is presumed that interaction of nucleophile with lanthanide 1,3-diketonates is pseudocontact in nature. In the course of time, the coordination angle of nucleophile with lanthanide 1,3-diketonates changes and as a result, a reversal of shifts produced has been noticed. It is well known that pseudocontact interaction is governed by McConnell and Robertson equation.

$$\Delta\delta = \frac{X3\cos^2\theta - 1}{r^3}$$

where r = nucleus-metal distance vector.

θ = the angle between this vector and the principal symmetry axis.

X = constant for a given metal adduct at a given temperature.

It predicts that if coordination angle is greater than 54.7°, a reversal of normal shifts is observed. The results are recorded in the Table 1.

In general, upfield shifts were produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *n*-hexanol. Shift

TABLE 1—SHIFT STUDIES ON *n*-HEXANOL, *p*-FLUOROANILINE BY Pr(pfp)₃, Pr(hfh)₃, Sm(pfp)₃ IN CDCl₃ (1 ml)

Sl. No.	Shift reagent	Nucleophile	Ratio of wt. in mg. (Shift reagent : nucleophile)	Time hr	Position of different signals in δ ppm					Aromatic protons
					-OH	-CH ₂ attached to -OH (CH ₂) ₄	-OH (CH ₂) ₄	CH ₂	-NH ₂	
1.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	Control	1	4.5	3.55	1.4	0.9		
2.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	2	2.0	3.15	1.15	0.75		
3.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	72	2.0	3.15	1.15	0.75		
4.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	Control	1	4.5	3.55	1.4	0.9		
5.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	2	3.1	3.5	1.35	0.9		
6.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	24	3.75	3.5	1.3	0.9		
7.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	6 : 1	26	3.75	3.5	1.3	0.9		
8.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	Control	1					3.5	6.8-7.0
9.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	1					2.95	6.4-7.0
10.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	24					2.90	6.4-7.0
11.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	Control	1					3.5	6.3-7.0
12.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	1					3.65	6.5-7.1
13.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	2					3.75	6.4-7.2

pfp = 4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato.

hfh = 4,4,5,5,6,6,6-heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato.

in OH was $\Delta\delta$ 2.5, CH₂ attached to -OH was 0.40, (CH₂)₄ 0.25 and CH₂ by 0.15 ppm. Positions of resonance signals remained unaltered after a long interval of time.

Shift produced by [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *n*-hexanol was downfield when the spectrum was taken after 2 hr. The following changes were noticed; -OH resonance signal shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 1.4, CH₂ attached to -OH by 0.05, (CH₂)₄ by 0.05 ppm and the CH₂ resonance signal remained unaltered. But when the same spectrum was taken after 24 hr, the position of -OH and (CH₂)₄ shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 0.65 and 0.1 ppm, respectively.

Upfield shift was produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *p*-fluoroaniline. Shift at the amino group was $\Delta\delta$ 0.6 ppm, while the shift produced for aromatic protons was very small, 0.1 ppm.

Downfield shift was produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]-samarium(III). Amino group resonance signal shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 0.15 and aromatic resonance signals by 0.2 ppm after 1 hr.

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Thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]-quinazolin-10-ones

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DIVERSE medicinal properties of thiazole derivatives¹⁻⁴ have prompted many synthetic chemists to prepare new compounds in which this ring is fused with other biologically important nuclei. It is with this aim that synthesis of thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one has been undertaken. The importance of triazole and quinazolinone is well known. The synthesis has been achieved as described below.

3-Amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I) on condensation with allyl isothiocyanate (II) gave rise to 3-allyl-1-[2-mercapto-4-oxo-3(4H)quinazoliny]-2-thiopseudourea (III), the structure of which finds support from pmr, analytical results and physical characteristics. In its pmr (CDCl₃+TFA) in δ scale, III showed a multiplet (2H), because of the allylic splitting, at 4.16 assignable to two allylic protons (-CH₂-CH=). It also exhibited another multiplet (2H) at 5.35-5.60 which could be attributed to two vinylic protons (-CH=CH₂). One vinylic proton (-CH=CH₂) and the four aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at 5.76-6.00 and 7.85-8.70, respectively. Moreover, the compound was soluble in aqueous NaOH and got reprecipitated on treatment with HCl indicating the presence of mercapto group in position 2. Treatment of III with bromine in glacial acetic acid resulted in the formation of 2-bromomethyl-2,3-dihydro-10H-thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (IV). The structure (IV) again has been confirmed on the basis of pmr data and analytical results. In its pmr (CDCl₃+TFA), IV showed a multiplet (5H) at 3.72-4.70 due to overlapping of signals of two methylene protons of bromomethyl group (-CH₂Br), one